

ANGREN-POP ELECTRIFIED RAILWAY IS A HIGH RESULT OF ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL COOPERATION.

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Annotation. The construction of the shortest railway line between Uzbekistan and China is one of the current strategic directions of economic and transport cooperation.

The main purpose of the construction of this railway is to create a single railway network of Uzbekistan. Another important aspect of this railway is the creation of favorable conditions for the regions of the Fergana Valley, which provides for comprehensive economic and social development.

Кейс вордс анд эхпрессиянс: railway, Angren-Pop, Whip Pass, tunnel, railway station, railway station, transit and tourism, passenger train, passenger transport , freight , workplace.

The construction of the shortest railway network between Uzbekistan and China is one of the current strategic ways of cooperation in the field of mutual economic and transport. This will ensure that China can enter Central Asian countries and then to South Asia. The construction of the Angren-Pop electrified railway will serve as a "bridge" in this regard. Uzbekistan Railways and China Railway Tunnel Group have electrified the 123.1-kilometer Angren-Pop railway . The launch of the Angren-Pop electrified railway line through the Kamchik Pass at an altitude of 2,200 meters above sea level will create an opportunity for goods and passenger transportation by rail between the Fergana Valley and other regions of the country. At the same time, it serves as the most important link in the new China-Central Asia-Europe international transit railway corridor . The Angren-Pop railway runs through the Kamchik Pass, connecting the three eastern regions of the country (Andijan, Namangan and Fergana) with the rest of Uzbekistan . The strategic task of the Angren-Pop railway is to complete the construction of a single railway network in the territory of the Republic and connect the regions of the Fergana Valley with a single transport system connecting the rest of the country .

A unique section of the steel track will be a 19.2-kilometer tunnel with a total cost of \$ 455 million. More than a thousand employees of China Railway Tunnel Group participated in its construction. Today, the only highway connecting the Fergana Valley of Uzbekistan near the border of the Republic of Tajikistan

passes through this tunnel. In addition to the tunnel, 43 million cubic meters of soil, 16.3 million cubic meters of drilling, 285 artificial facilities, 22 bridges and 6 overpasses have been built here. In addition, 6 railway stations and two railway stations were built. On the basis of the project, 285 artificial structures and water pipes, 13 railway bridges with a total length of 2.1 km, 6 overpasses, 4 railway stations, 4 railway stations and 2 railway stations, 2 substations were built completed. The Angren-Pop electrified railway line is one of the top eight in the world in terms of complexity and the first 13 in terms of the length of tunnels being built under the project. Orzu, Temryulobod, Kul, Kushminor stations have been built on this railway. The \$ 1.769 billion project used up to \$ 1 billion in loans from international financial institutions, with the rest financed by Uzbekistan.

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More than a thousand specialists of China Railway Tunnel Group, more than three thousand railway workers, more than three hundred electricians took part in the creative work.

The Angren-Pop electrified railway plays a special role in the further development and prosperity of our country. It is estimated that the railway will be able to handle 600,000 passengers this year alone. While 4,000 people were employed during the construction period, another 1,500 new jobs will be created when the railway becomes operational. The implementation of such a large and important project as the construction of the Angren-Pop electrified railway serves to strengthen the economic power of our country, increase transit and tourism potential and further develop the railway network.

Today, modern high-speed passenger trains serve the population on this route every day on the route Tashkent - Andijan - Tashkent. There are two passenger trains a week on the Andijan-Bukhara-Andijan route, and once a week on the Andijan-Urgench-Andijan, Andijan-Moscow-Andijan routes. In addition, dozens of freight trains a day pass through the Angren-Pop electrified railway, delivering cargo to its destination.

In particular, according to the information service of Uzbekistan Railways, the railway has so far served more than 413,162 passengers and transported 7.396 million tons of cargo. It also created 1,718 new jobs.

In short, the construction of the Angren-Pop electrified railway is huge and very important. The construction of the railway will serve to strengthen the economic power of our country, increase transit and tourism potential and further develop the railway network, as well as to raise the multifaceted, strategic relations between Uzbekistan and China to a higher level and continuous development.

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